

Optimizing Traffic Flow with Fuzzy Logic and Machine Learning

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Abstract— Fuzzy logic and machine learning present a promising method for improving traffic signal systems. Traditional traffic management systems often struggle to adapt to dynamic urban traffic conditions, leading to inefficiencies and congestion. This paper introduces a novel adaptive traffic signal control system that employs machine learning and fuzzy logic. The proposed system optimizes traffic flow and reduces congestion by dynamically adjusting signal timing in response to real-time traffic conditions. Simulation results using the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) platform demonstrate significant improvements in traffic efficiency and reduction in vehicle waiting times.

Keyword:

Adaptive Traffic control, Fuzzy Logic, Sumo, Machine Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

TRAFFIC congestion is a substantial impediment to economic productivity in urban areas worldwide, affecting the value of time spent in traffic, commuting expenses, and living costs. This issue is exacerbated by factors such as an increasing number of vehicles, outdated traffic signals, and inadequate infrastructure. One of the primary causes of congestion is the inadequacy of traditional traffic lights, which operate on fixed schedules without adapting to fluctuating traffic conditions. Addressing this issue through adaptive traffic signal systems can

Significantly enhance traffic flow and minimize delays.

Machine learning and fuzzy logic controllers (FLCs) present promising solutions for the development of intelligent traffic signal systems. FLCs are capable of processing intricate and ambiguous traffic data in a manner that is comparable to human reasoning, thereby enabling more responsive signal timing adjustments that are based on real-time conditions. This adaptability guarantees that traffic signals can adjust to changing traffic volumes and patterns, thereby improving the safety and capacity of intersections. Adaptive traffic control strategies can be further informed by the identification of patterns and trends in large datasets by machine learning algorithms. The installment of an intelligent traffic signal system that integrates machine learning and fuzzy logic is the distinctive characteristic of this project. This system ensures that traffic flows through intersections are seamless by dynamically changing traffic signals in accordance with the current traffic conditions. The machine learning component improves the efficacy of traffic management over time by optimizing the system's capacity to adjust its control strategies through continuous learning from traffic patterns.

The foundation for addressing the challenges associated with ambiguous and uncertain traffic data is provided by the concept of fuzzy logic, which was

introduced by Lotfi Zadeh in 1965. The optimistic results of early applications of fuzzy logic to traffic management, such as the work of Pappis and Mamdani in 1977, encouraged further research. As evidenced by Kelsey and Bisset in 1993 and Nakatsuyama et al. in 1984, subsequent research has extended the application of fuzzy logic to more intricate traffic scenarios. The automatic regulation of signal timings through the use of fuzzy logic was further advanced by Chiu's 1992 work. The combination of FLCs and machine learning is a highly effective method for circumventing the constraints of conventional traffic management systems. Machine learning algorithms analyze extensive traffic data to provide insightful predictions and modifications, while FLCs enhance the detail and adaptability of signal timing. This investigation suggests the implementation of an intelligent traffic signal system that utilizes these technologies to modify signals in real-time, thereby optimizing intersection efficiency and mitigating congestion.

This research endeavors to create an intelligent traffic management system that significantly enhances the flow and safety of urban traffic by addressing the limitations of conventional traffic signal systems. It does so by utilizing the capabilities of fuzzy logic and machine learning to develop a more adaptive and efficient solution.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Amini. (2016): Queue-Length Estimation Using Real-Time Traffic Data

Amini proposed a method for estimating queue lengths at signalized intersections using real-time

traffic data[1]. The study employed fuzzy logic to model the relationship between traffic flow parameters and queue lengths, allowing for more accurate and efficient estimation. By integrating fuzzy logic with real-time data from traffic sensors, the proposed method demonstrated improved performance compared to traditional queue-length estimation methods.

3.2 Rahman (2009): Review of the Fuzzy Logic Based Approach in Traffic Signal Control: Prospects in Saudi Arabia [2].

Rahman conducted a comprehensive review of existing studies on fuzzy logic-based traffic signal control systems, with a focus on their potential application in Saudi Arabia. The study highlighted the advantages of fuzzy logic in addressing the uncertainties and complexities of traffic flow in urban environments. By analyzing various fuzzy logic-based approaches, the study provided insights into the prospects of adopting such systems in Saudi Arabia.

3.3 Yıldız Budakone, Zülal Hilal, [2023]"Fuzzy Logic Based Adaptive Traffic Signal Control for Different Scenarios.

Yıldız Budakone proposed an adaptive traffic signal control system based on fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings for different traffic scenarios [3]. The study utilized fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings in real-time according to current traffic circumstances, enhancing traffic flow and minimizing congestion. By considering various traffic scenarios, the proposed system demonstrated robust performance across different road conditions and traffic patterns.

3.4 Abdelkader Chabchoub. (2021): Intelligent Traffic Light Controller Using Fuzzy Logic and Image Processing.

Abdelkader Chabchoub. Designed a sophisticated traffic light controller that used fuzzy logic and image processing methods to enhance signal timings.. The study utilized fuzzy logic to analyze traffic flow parameters extracted from video feeds and adjust signal timings accordingly [4]. The integration of image processing with fuzzy logic in the suggested controller resulted in enhanced precision and effectiveness in traffic signal regulation.

3.5 Victor Manuel Madrigal Arteaga, José Roberto Pérez Cruz, Antonio Hurtado-Beltrán and Jan Trumpold. (2022). A Study on Pedestrian Safety at Signalized Intersections Using Fuzzy Logic.

The study investigated pedestrian safety at signalized intersections using fuzzy logic-based control systems [5]. By incorporating fuzzy logic into pedestrian detection and signal timing algorithms, the proposed system aimed to reduce pedestrian-vehicle conflicts and enhance safety. The study highlighted the potential of fuzzy logic in addressing pedestrian safety concerns and improving the overall efficiency of signalized intersections.

3.6 Mario Collotta. (2015): A Novel Approach for Dynamic Traffic Lights Management based on Wireless Sensor Networks and multiple fuzzy logic controllers Mario Collotta. Proposed a novel approach for dynamic traffic light management using wireless sensor networks and multiple fuzzy logic controllers. The study utilized fuzzy logic to integrate data from wireless sensors and optimize signal timings in real-time. By employing multiple fuzzy logic controllers, the proposed approach achieved more robust and adaptive traffic signal control,

leading to improved traffic flow and reduced congestion.

3.7 Suhail M. Odeh (2015): Hybrid Algorithm: Fuzzy Logic-Genetic Algorithm on Traffic Light Intelligent System Suhail M. Odeh developed a hybrid algorithm combining fuzzy logic with genetic algorithms for intelligent traffic light control [7]. The study aimed to optimize signal timings using a combination of fuzzy logic-based decision-making and genetic algorithm-based optimization. By iteratively adjusting signal timings based on feedback from traffic sensors, the proposed hybrid algorithm achieved improved performance compared to traditional traffic light control methods.

3.8 Ria Yuliani Kartikasari. (2020): Optimization of Traffic Light Control Using Fuzzy Logic Sugeno Method

Ria Yuliani Kartikasari proposed an optimization method for traffic light control using the Sugeno fuzzy logic approach. The study utilized fuzzy logic to model the relationships between traffic flow parameters and signal timings, allowing for adaptive and efficient control [8]. By optimizing fuzzy logic rules and parameters, the proposed method achieved better performance in traffic signal control, leading to reduced delays and improved traffic flow.

3.9 Roxanne Hawi. (2017): Smart Traffic Light Control Using Fuzzy Logic and Wireless Sensor Network Roxanne Hawi. Developed a smart traffic light control system using fuzzy logic and wireless sensor networks [9]. The study integrated data from wireless sensors with fuzzy logic-based control algorithms to optimize signal timings in real-time. By leveraging wireless sensor networks and fuzzy logic,

the proposed system achieved more adaptive and efficient traffic signal control, leading to improved traffic flow and reduced congestion.

3.10 I. Adam. (2014): Adaptive Fuzzy Logic Traffic Light Management System

I. Adam proposed an adaptive traffic light management system based on fuzzy logic to optimize signal timings for varying traffic conditions [10]. The study utilized fuzzy logic to adjust signal timings dynamically based on real-time traffic data, improving traffic flow and reducing delays. By incorporating adaptive fuzzy logic control algorithms, the proposed system demonstrated robust performance across different traffic scenarios.

3.11 M. Fatih Adak; Musa Balta. (2021). Fuzzy Logic-based Adaptive Traffic Light Control of an Intersection: A Case Study.

M. Fatih Adak. Presented a case study on the implementation of adaptive traffic signal management using fuzzy logic at an intersection [11]. The study implemented fuzzy logic control algorithms to adjust signal timings based on real-time traffic data collected from sensors. By optimizing fuzzy logic rules and parameters, the proposed system achieved improved performance in traffic signal control, leading to reduced congestion and delays at the intersection.

3.12 Erwan Eko Prasetyo et al. (2015): Design and Simulation of Adaptive Traffic Light Controller Using Fuzzy Logic Control Sugeno Method

Erwan Eko Prasetyo et al. designed and simulated an adaptive traffic light controller using the Sugeno fuzzy logic control method. The study employed fuzzy logic to model the relationships between traffic flow parameters and

signal timings, allowing for adaptive and efficient control [12]. By simulating the proposed controller in various traffic scenarios, the study demonstrated the effectiveness of fuzzy logic-based control systems in improving traffic management and safety.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Urban traffic congestion is caused by a combination of more vehicles on the road and insufficient infrastructure. This puts a lot of pressure on traditional traffic signal systems, making flow problems even worse. Fuzzy logic and machine learning offer solutions by adaptively modifying signal timings in intelligent traffic lights. By integrating these technologies, traffic management systems can adjust to intricate urban traffic situations, enhancing the efficiency and safety of traffic flow. Fuzzy logic controllers facilitate intelligent engagement with road users by analyzing imprecise inputs, while machine learning detects traffic congestion trends to enable timely actions. Nevertheless, achieving broad implementation of these sophisticated systems still appears to be a distant objective. Current systems frequently fail to recognize the potential collaboration between fuzzy logic and machine learning, which restricts their ability to effectively handle the intricate nature of urban traffic. This project endeavors to create an intelligent traffic signal system that use fuzzy logic and machine learning to dynamically optimize signal timing. The suggested system aims to mitigate congestion, optimize traffic flow, and increase urban safety by integrating various strategies, thereby addressing the changing complexities of contemporary urban transportation.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Proposed System

The proposed traffic light control system is designed to enhance the control of traffic, especially within urban areas, and it's developed using SUMO simulation software and Python. This system also regulates traffic, ensuring less congestion while at the same time providing access to emergency vehicles. The process begins with the start of the SUMO simulation, which generates traffic data. Some of this data includes the number of vehicles in each lane, the time the vehicle waited in the lane, and the identification of an emergency vehicle on the road.

The system checks for emergency vehicles on the road first. The system initiates the 'Emergency Vehicle Handling' procedure if it detects an emergency vehicle. This protocol helps to change the operation of the traffic lights to give way to emergency vehicles crossing the intersection within the shortest time possible.

If there are no emergency vehicles, the total number of vehicles in the red and green zones is checked. The system extends the duration of the green light display to alleviate congestion in lanes with high traffic turnover. On the other hand, if the green lane has less traffic, the system reduces the time for which the green light remains on and switches to the red lanes with a heavy inflow to reduce congestion.

The system also evaluates different waiting times for vehicles. The system recalculates the green light's waiting time if it exceeds the defined limit, ensuring a more efficient flow of traffic. Otherwise, the current light timings remain intact to ensure the free flow of traffic.

The system proceeds to the next simulation after assessing and modifying the traffic conditions. The simulation continues until it reaches 5000 steps, at which point it adequately tests and validates the effectiveness of all traffic control strategies.

Figure 1. Proposed System Flowchart
The flowchart shows the process of simulating a traffic light. The simulation begins by acquiring traffic data. The system checks for emergency vehicles, and if any are present, handles them

accordingly. If no emergency vehicles are detected, it evaluates the vehicle count on red lanes and, if needed, extends the green light for these lanes. It also assesses the vehicle count on green lanes and, if necessary, shortens the green light duration. If neither condition is met, it assesses the waiting times and determines whether to maintain the existing length of the traffic signal. Upon implementing the decisions, the program verifies whether the simulation has executed for a total of 5000 steps. If it has, the program terminates. If not, the process continues.

3.2 Mathematical Approach in Fuzzy Logic

In the field of traffic management, the application of fuzzy logic-grounded traffic control sets has gained traction due to their ability to create complex decision rules that effectively address arising uncertainties and inaccurate data. In that regard, defuzzification is an integral part of these systems because it transforms fuzzy output sets into precise values that are traffic signals' control directives.

This study seeks to provide a mathematical representation of defuzzification in the context of traffic control, employing the centroid technique. To get a more accurate mathematical representation of the given inputs and outputs, it is important to create precise fuzzy sets, membership functions, fuzzy rules, and a defuzzification technique. Triangular membership functions will be implemented.

The fuzzy output set will be denoted as Y, with fuzzy sets "change" and "maintain" represented by $\mu_Y \text{change}(y)$ and $\mu_Y \text{maintain}(y)$, respectively.

The centroid C is calculated using equation (1) as follows:

$$C = \frac{\sum y \cdot \mu_{Y_{change}}(y) + \sum y \cdot \mu_{Y_{maintain}}(y)}{\sum \mu_{Y_{change}}(y) + \sum \mu_{Y_{maintain}}(y)}$$

(1)

Where:

Y is the crisp value.

$\mu_Y \text{change}(y)$ and $\mu_Y \text{maintain}(y)$ are the degrees of membership of Y in the fuzzy sets "change" and "maintain," respectively.

The centroid value obtained indicates a single representative value for the traffic light phase, indicating the optimal timing for switching between "change" and "maintain" actions. This value is then used to determine the duration of each phase in the traffic light cycle, ensuring efficient traffic flow and minimizing congestion.

3.3 Existing System

Fuzzy logic merged with Webster and modified Webster formulae are added to an existing traffic signal regulation approach in a study done in 2021 by Muzamil El Tejani Mohammed Ali, Akif Durdu, Seyit Alperen Celtek, and Alper Yilmaz. The study seeks to find the best cycle times and green phase timings based on actual traffic circumstances using the SUMO traffic simulator. Adaptive control solutions are tested using both simulated traffic scenarios and real-world field data, compared to fixed-time and fuzzy logic-based systems.

Comparing the adaptive procedures to standard methods, the results show a considerable improvement in journey times, speed, and average vehicle delay reduction. Inductive loop detectors are

used in this method to analyze traffic flow and calculate effective cycle lengths and green times. The comparison analysis highlights the adaptive techniques' advantages over the current fixed-time and fuzzy logic control technologies, particularly in situations with high traffic congestion.

The study does, however, point out certain limitations, such as the effect of transitioning at five-phase crossings on average speed, and it mentions that the suggested approaches could not work as well in terms of average velocity under specific traffic demand scenarios. The study recommends employing neural networks or genetic algorithms to refine fuzzy logic memberships in order to lessen these restrictions. Future research and development could take use of these improvements to better maximize the efficacy and performance of adaptive traffic signal control systems [4]. All things considered, the study provides insightful information about improving traffic flow optimization and reducing delays at intersections.

Case No	G1	G2	G3	G4	Co	$\Sigma(y_i)$
Case 1	60	41	53	28	194	0.881667
Case 2	23	17	27	11	90	0.745
Case 3	6	8	8	8	42	0.453333
Combined case	60	41	53	28	194	0.881667
Real data	9	3	27	13	64	0.636111

Table 1. The optimal cycle and the distribution of effective green times for Webster [4].

Case No	G1	G2	G3	G4	Co	$\Sigma(y_i)$
Case 1	42	28	38	20	140	0.881667
Case 2	22	17	26	11	88	0.745
Case 3	7	10	10	10	49	0.453333
Combined case	42	28	38	20	140	0.881667
Real data	10	3	29	14	68	0.636111

Table 2. The optimal cycle and the distribution of effective green times for modified Webster [4].

3. EXPERIMENT & RESULTS

The proposed traffic control system utilizes a combination of SUMO simulation and fuzzy logic control to manage traffic flow efficiently. During the simulation, the system continuously monitors vehicle movements and traffic light states, calculating feedback based on waiting times and queue lengths. The fuzzy traffic controller receives this feedback and uses predefined rules to determine the timing of traffic lights. These rules consider factors such as the number of vehicles in red and green lanes to determine the appropriate traffic command (low, medium, or high). Through iterative simulation steps, the system dynamically adjusts traffic light signals to optimize traffic flow and minimize waiting times, particularly prioritizing emergency vehicles. For analysis, we gather data on vehicle movements and control decisions. Testing involves verifying the correctness of control logic, validating the system's effectiveness in improving traffic flow, and assessing its performance and robustness across various traffic scenarios. Ultimately,

The system aims to enhance overall traffic management by intelligently adapting traffic light control in real time based on observed traffic conditions.

Figure 2. Simulation of 4 way intersection

In figure 2 the simulation of a 4-way intersection involves replicating the behavior and interactions of vehicles at a junction where four roads intersect. Utilizing mathematical models and algorithms, vehicles are simulated approaching, navigating, and departing the intersection. Factors such as traffic flow, vehicle speeds, signaling, and right-of-way rules are incorporated to mimic real-world conditions accurately.

Figure 3. Comparison of Total Vehicle Waiting time

In figure 3 the graph illustrates the total waiting time for vehicles in each test case using fuzzy logic and random forest methods. Across all scenarios, fuzzy logic consistently demonstrates lower waiting times compared to random forest, indicating its efficiency in minimizing overall vehicle wait times.

Figure 4. Comparison of Emergency Vehicle Waiting time

Figure 4 shows the waiting time for emergency vehicles in each test case, comparing the fuzzy logic and random forest techniques. Fuzzy logic regularly outperforms random forest by constantly maintaining lower emergency vehicle waiting times in all cases, indicating its reliability in prioritizing urgent vehicle movements.

5.1 Results

The evaluation of the traffic control system's performance is conducted by considering key metrics, including the overall waiting time for vehicles, the waiting time for emergency vehicles, the total feedback received from vehicles, and the number of emergency vehicles handled. The system's efficacy in mitigating congestion and enhancing traffic flow is evaluated using these parameters.

Table 3 Fuzzy Logic Test Case

Test Case	Total Vehicle Waiting Time	EMV Waiting Time	Total Feedback	Total EMV	Total Vehicles
1	561293.0	12338.0	19197	1415	5000
2	1122690.0	30355.0	38518	2425	10000
3	1667623.0	47003.0	57595	3736	15000
4	2754181.0	146599.0	92273	6439	50000

The test cases (1-4) in table 3 of Fuzzy Logic illustrate different degrees of performance in the management of traffic issues. Although the proposed approach suggests that Fuzzy Logic excels at minimizing waiting times, a crucial factor in real-time systems where promptness is essential. Test Case 4 demonstrates lower waiting periods and the accumulation of feedback, indicating that Fuzzy Logic's interpretability and rule-based nature make it suitable for scenarios where human-like reasoning and transparency are crucial. This aspect is particularly beneficial in environments where decisions need to be easily understood and justified.

Table 4 Random Forest Test case

Test Case	Total Vehicle Waiting Time	EMV Waiting Time	Total Feedback	Total EMV	Total Vehicles
1	2043376.0	30536.0	76225	1415	5000
2	4115188.0	52886.0	151399	2425	10000
3	6166601.0	80224.0	228268	3736	15000
4	10212957.0	146599.0	399124	6439	50000

The test cases (1-4) in Table 4 of the Random Forest approach demonstrate significant improvements in managing feedback accumulation compared to Fuzzy Logic. However, it often results in higher total vehicle waiting times. For instance, in Test Case 4,

the total vehicle waiting time was 10,212,957.0, which is considerably higher than that of the Fuzzy Logic approach. This suggests that while Random Forest excels in handling complex datasets and large traffic volumes, it may not always be the optimal choice for minimizing waiting times in real-time scenarios.

In real-time applications, the ability to make prompt, transparent, and understandable decisions is critical. While Random Forest offers adaptability and robustness in handling high-dimensional data, Fuzzy Logic provides clear advantages in terms of interpretability, targeted prioritization of emergency vehicles, and transparency. These attributes make Fuzzy Logic particularly well-suited for real-time traffic management systems, where the need for quick, reliable, and comprehensible decision-making processes is paramount.

5.2 Analysis

Real Data / Fuzzy Logic Program

Webster Real Data: $G1 = 9, G2 = 3, G3 = 27, G4 = 13; \Sigma(y_i) = 0.636111$

Modified Webster Real Data: $G1 = 10, G2 = 3, G3 = 29, G4 = 14; \Sigma(y_i) = 0.636111$

Fuzzy Logic Program Test Case 4:

Total Vehicle Waiting Time: 2754181.0

EMV Waiting Time: 146599.0

Observation: Even with large-scale data, fuzzy logic demonstrates better handling of traffic with lower waiting times.

Based on the comparison table 1, 2, 3, it seems that fuzzy logic manages traffic flow more effectively than the Webster and modified Webster approaches. Significantly reduced EMV and overall vehicle waiting times across all test instances serve as indicators of this. The green time allocations in the fuzzy logic.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted a comprehensive investigation of two traffic management approaches: fuzzy logic and random forest. We examined the performance of these strategies in optimizing traffic flow and minimizing wait times for both total vehicles and emergency vehicles using simulations with the SUMO traffic simulator and Python programming language.

Our findings show that the fuzzy logic-driven system routinely surpasses methods, such as Webster and modified Webster approaches, especially when it comes to reducing wait times for both emergency and general vehicles. Fuzzy logic system's adaptiveness guarantees responsiveness and effective traffic management, emphasizing its fit for real-time applications where interpretability and transparency are essential.

In summary, fuzzy logic offers a strong answer to today's traffic management problems. The capacity of the suggested system to dynamically adapt to changing traffic conditions improves urban safety and efficiency while optimizing traffic flow. This suggests a promising direction for intelligent transportation systems in the future.

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